

AI-Generated Code Integration Feasibility: An Empirical Study

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Appendix A: Detailed Results of the Empirical Study

The following tables report detailed results of the empirical study for all evaluated algorithms. Algorithms are grouped according to their corresponding **TheAlgorithms** packages, reflecting the structural organization of the target codebase.

Legend

Compile

compilation status (pass / fail)

Test

test execution result (pass / fail / n/a = in case compilation failed)

Notes

brief description of dominant failure cause (if applicable)

Sorting Algorithms (`com.thealgorithms.sorts`)

Scenario A

- compilation succeeded for `QuickSort`, `CountingSort` and `RadixSort`
- only `QuickSort` and `CountingSort` passed the tests

Table 1. Appendix A (Sorting) — Scenario A detailed outcomes.

Algorithm	Compile	Test	Notes
QuickSort	pass	pass	—
BubbleSort	fail	n/a	cannot find symbol: Sort
CountingSort	pass	pass	—
HeapSort	fail	n/a	cannot find symbol: Sort
InsertionSort	fail	n/a	does not override abstract method sort
MergeSort	fail	n/a	does not override abstract method sort
RadixSort	pass	fail	fails for negative numbers
SelectionSort	fail	n/a	cannot find symbol: Sort

Scenario B

- all algorithms succeeded in compilation and all tests

Table 2. Appendix A (Sorting) — Scenario B detailed outcomes.

Algorithm	Compile	Test	Notes
QuickSort	pass	pass	—
BubbleSort	pass	pass	—
CountingSort	pass	pass	—
HeapSort	pass	pass	—
InsertionSort	pass	pass	—
MergeSort	pass	pass	—
RadixSort	pass	pass	—
SelectionSort	pass	pass	—

Data Structures (com.thealgorithms.datastructures)

Scenario A

- compilation succeeded for `HashMap` and `DoublyLinkedList`
- only `DoublyLinkedList` passed the tests

Table 3. Appendix A (Data Structures) — Scenario A detailed outcomes.

Algorithm	Compile	Test	Notes
HashMap	pass	fail	null-key semantics mismatch
MaxHeap	fail	n/a	duplicate class Heap
DoublyLinkedList	pass	pass	—
SinglyLinkedList	fail	n/a	constructor mismatch

Algorithm	Compile	Test	Notes
Queue	fail	n/a	unresolved generic type T
StackArray	fail	n/a	unresolved generic type T
DisjointSetUnion	fail	n/a	duplicate class Node

Scenario B

- compilation succeeded for all algorithms
- 4 of 7 algorithms passed the tests

Table 4. Appendix A (Data Structures) — Scenario B detailed outcomes.

Algorithm	Tests failed of total	Notes
HashMap	pass	—
MaxHeap	fail	hangs
DoublyLinkedList	pass	—
SinglyLinkedList	3 of 16	SinglyLinkedListTest.middle:61 expected: <4> but was: <5>, SinglyLinkedListTest.toStringForEmptyListTest:244 expected: <> but was: <[]>, SinglyLinkedListTest.toStringTest:238 expected: <1 → 2 → 3> but was: <[1, 2, 3]>
Queue	pass	—
StackArray	1 of 15	bad toString format: testToString:127 expected: <StackArray [1, 2, 3]> but was: <[1, 2, 3]>
DisjointSetUnion	pass	—

Graph Algorithms

(com.thealgorithms.datastructures.graphs)

Scenario A

- compilation succeeded for `FordFulkerson`, `PrimMST`, and `TarjansAlgorithm`
- the same ones also passed the tests

Table 5. Appendix A (Graphs) — Scenario A detailed outcomes.

Algorithm	Compile	Test	Notes
BellmanFord	fail	n/a	compilation error
FloydWarshall	fail	n/a	missing INFINITY constant
FordFulkerson	pass	pass	—
Kruskal	fail	n/a	private access to Edge.from
TarjansAlgorithm	pass	pass	—

Algorithm	Compile	Test	Notes
PrimMST	pass	pass	—
TopologicalSort	fail	n/a	incorrect output ordering

Scenario B

- compilation succeeded for all algorithms

Table 6. Appendix A (Graphs) — Scenario B detailed outcomes.

Algorithm	Tests failed of total	Notes
BellmanFord	pass	—
FloydWarshall	pass	—
FordFulkerson	pass	—
Kruskal	2 of 4	testGraphWithDisconnectedNodes:111, testKruskal:71
TarjansAlgorithm	pass	—
PrimMST	pass	—
TopologicalSort	3 of 4	bad output format: <Graph contains a cycle; topological ordering is not possible.> but was: <This graph contains a cycle. No linear ordering is possible. Back edge: 6 → 2>

Tree Algorithms

(`com.thealgorithms.datastructures.trees`)

Scenario A

- compilation succeeded for one algorithm (`AVLTree`)

Table 7. Appendix A (Trees) — Scenario A detailed outcomes.

Algorithm	Compile and Test	Notes
AVLTree	pass	—
BinaryTree	compile fail	compile of many other types failed on <code>com.thealgorithms.datastructures.trees.BinaryTree.Node</code>

Scenario B

- compilation succeeded for one algorithm (`AVLTree`)

Table 8. Appendix A (Trees) — Scenario B detailed outcomes.

Algorithm	Compile and Test	Notes
AVLTree	pass	—

Algorithm	Compile and Test	Notes
BinaryTree	compile fail	compile of many other types failed on <code>com.thealgorithms.datastructures.trees.BinaryTree.Node</code>

Searching Algorithms (`com.thealgorithms.searches`)

Scenario A

- compilation succeeded for only one algorithm (`KMP`)

Table 9. Appendix A (Searching) — Scenario A compilation outcomes.

Algorithm	Compile failure reason
BinarySearch	compilation error
BreadthFirstSearch	missing Node class
DepthFirstSearch	unresolved generic type T
LinearSearch	unresolved generic type T
KMP	pass

Scenario B

- compilation succeeded for all algorithms except of `LinearSearch`
- all tests passed for all compiled algorithms

Table 10. Appendix A (Searching) — Scenario B outcomes.

Algorithm	Tests failed of total	Reason
BinarySearch	pass	—
BreadthFirstSearch	pass	—
DepthFirstSearch	pass	—
LinearSearch	compile failed	LinearSearch is not abstract and does not override abstract method <code><T>find(T[], T)</code> in <code>com.thealgorithms.devutils.searches.SearchAlgorithm</code>
KMP	pass	—

Dynamic Programming (`com.thealgorithms.dynamicprogramming`)

Scenario A

- compilation succeeded for all algorithms
- test failed for all algorithms except of `LongestIncreasingSubsequence` where it succeeded

Table 11. Appendix A (Dynamic Programming) — Scenario A outcomes.

Algorithm	Tests failed of total	Reason
CoinChange	2 of 9	incorrect impossible-case handling
EditDistance	3 of 15	multiple string comparison failures
KadaneAlgorithm	1 of 6	empty array handling
Knapsack	4 of 8	wrong exception type
LongestCommonSubsequence	1+3 of 9	null input causes NPE
LongestIncreasingSubsequence	pass	—
MatrixChainMultiplication	2 errors of 3	array index out of bounds
RodCutting	2 of 8	missing exception on empty input

Scenario B

- compilation succeeded for all remaining algorithms
- test failed again for most of them, see next Table

Table 12. Appendix A (Dynamic Programming) — Scenario B outcomes.

Algorithm	Tests failed of total	Reason
CoinChange	2 of 9	bad error indication
EditDistance	3 of 15	bad results
KadaneAlgorithm	1 of 6	another runtime exception thrown
Knapsack	2 of 8	runtime exception not thrown on invalid input
LongestCommonSubsequence	pass	—
LongestIncreasingSubsequence	pass	—
MatrixChainMultiplication	2 errors of 3	Incompatible matrix chain
RodCutting	pass	—

Mathematics and Conversions ([com.thealgorithms.maths](#), [conversions](#))

Scenario A

- compilation succeeded for all algorithms
- test failed for all algorithms except of [InverseOfMatrix](#) where it succeeded

Table 13. Appendix A (Math and Conversions) — Scenario A outcomes.

Algorithm	Tests failed of total	Reason
DecimalToHexadecimal	4 of 8	lowercase vs uppercase output
RomanToInteger	3 of 8	invalid lowercase handling, no exceptions
Factorial	1 of 2	incorrect exception message
FastExponentiation	2 of 6	wrong exception type
GCD	3 of 11	missing exception on invalid input
SieveOfEratosthenes	1 of 8	missing exception on negative input
InverseOfMatrix	pass	—
MatrixMultiplication	1 of 9	null input handling

Scenario B

- compilation succeeded for all remaining algorithms
- test failed again for most of them, see next Table

Table 14. Appendix A (Math and Conversions) — Scenario B outcomes.

Algorithm	Tests failed of total	Reason
DecimalToHexadecimal	4 of 8	lowercase vs uppercase output
RomanToInteger	1 error of 8	Invalid Roman character: v
Factorial	1 of 2	incorrect exception message
FastExponentiation	pass	—
GCD	3+1 of 11	err on empty input handling; missing exception on invalid input
SieveOfEratosthenes	pass	—
InverseOfMatrix	pass	—
MatrixMultiplication	1 of 9	null input handling

Classical Problems and Miscellaneous

([com.thealgorithms.backtracking](#),
[com.thealgorithms.bitmanipulation](#),
[com.thealgorithms.compression](#),
[com.thealgorithms.puzzlesandgames](#))

Scenario A

- compilation succeeded for all algorithms

- test failed for **LZW** and **TowerOfHanoi**

Table 15. Appendix A (Miscellaneous) — Scenario A outcomes.

Algorithm	Compile	Test	Notes
NQueens	pass	pass	—
Permutation	pass	pass	—
ReverseBits	pass	pass	—
LZW	pass	fail	invalid compressed data handling
TowerOfHanoi	pass	fail	output format mismatch

Scenario B

- compilation succeeded for all algorithms
- test failed for **LZW**

Table 16. Appendix A (Miscellaneous) — Scenario B outcomes.

Algorithm	Tests failed of total	Notes
NQueens	pass	—
Permutation	pass	—
ReverseBits	pass	—
LZW	2 of 7	LZWTest.testDecompressionWithGapInDictionary:102 Expected java.lang.IllegalArgumentException to be thrown, but nothing was thrown. LZWTest.testInvalidCompressedData:89 Expected java.lang.IllegalArgumentException to be thrown, but nothing was thrown.
TowerOfHanoi	pass	—